

of ovicidal action of a molluscicide on GAS.

This technique would likely reduce the total consumption of molluscicide by 80% ha⁻¹, ultimately increasing farmers' savings on labor, time, and energy while reducing other unforeseen environmental hazards. In addition, a drastic reduction in early first-generation GAS eggs to hatch, combined with other known management options,

would push the multiplication of destructive GAS back 1–2 mo, when rice plants are not vulnerable to them anymore.

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Evaluation of preemergence herbicides for weed control in wet-seeded rice

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Economic factors, such as the rising labor cost for transplanting and recent changes in rice production technology by intensification through double or triple cropping, have improved the desirability of direct seeding of rice under puddled conditions, although transplanting is still a major traditional method of crop establishment under lowland conditions (Pandey and Velasco 1999). Direct sowing of pregerminated seeds after puddling in lowlands is termed "wet seeding." Competition from weeds is a major constraint to the productivity of wet-seeded rice because rice has no growth advantage over weeds, as in transplanted rice. Grass weeds are also more difficult to hand weed at the transplanting stage because of their similar morphology to that of rice. Weeds have been reported to reduce the yield of wet-seeded rice by 15–70%. Direct-seeded rice covers 26% and 28% of the total rice area in South Asia and India, respectively (Pandey and Velasco

1999). It may become more popular if an effective weed control system is developed. The nonavailability of labor at the critical period of crop-weed competition and increased labor costs present problems at weeding in wet-seeded rice. At present, although many herbicides are available for transplanted rice, their effectiveness in wet-seeded rice has not been evaluated as a replacement for the traditional hand weeding, with its high labor requirement. This study was thus conducted to evaluate the performance of different pre-emergence herbicides for effective weed control in wet-seeded rice in places where labor is scanty and costly.

The experiments were done at the Regional Research Station, Paiyur, on red sandy loam soils. The first was in the 1999 wet season (Aug to Dec) and the second in the 2000 dry season (Dec to Apr). Five pre-emergence herbicides—butachlor at 1.0 kg ai ha⁻¹ (T₃), butanil at 1.0 kg ai ha⁻¹

(T₄), pretilachlor at 0.4 kg ai ha⁻¹ (T₅), pretilachlor + safener at 0.4 kg ai ha⁻¹ (T₆), and anilophos at 0.3 kg ai ha⁻¹ (T₇)—were compared against hand weeding at 20 d after sowing (DAS) (T₂) and no weeding (T₁). The trial was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. The dwarf (65 cm) indica variety, ADT43 (110 d), was direct-seeded through a drum seeder at 60 kg ha⁻¹. The required quantity of herbicide was mixed with sand at 50 kg ha⁻¹ and applied 8 DAS as a normal recommended practice. Weed samples were collected randomly from four places in a plot in a 1-m² area and weed dry weight was assessed on an oven-dry-weight basis. Data on various parameters were statistically analyzed; wherever treatment differences were significant by the F test, critical differences were computed at the 5% probability level and compared.

The dominant weeds found in the experimental field were *Cyperus rotundus*, *C. iria*, *C.*

difformis, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *E. colona*, *Marsilea quadrifolia*, *Eclipta alba*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, and *Astracantha longifolia*. The application of butanil, pretilachlor, and anilophos significantly resulted in less weeds and dry weight of weeds at 40 DAS compared with the unweeded check and hand-weeded plot (Table 1). The weed control efficiency (WCE) was higher in all herbicide-applied plots compared with the unweeded check and hand weeding. However, WCE was comparatively higher in butanil, followed by anilophos and pretilachlor. In direct-seeded puddled rice, Angiras and Rana (1998) found butachlor (2 kg ai ha⁻¹) + safener (0.188 kg ai ha⁻¹) to be the most effective combination for controlling weeds.

In general, the application of herbicides resulted in a significantly higher grain (3–12%) and straw yield over hand weeding. Anilophos, pretilachlor, and butanil recorded a maximum mean grain yield of 5.3 t ha⁻¹ compared with other herbicides. However, Nandal and Hari (1998) found that the treatment of pretilachlor at 1.0 kg ai ha⁻¹ registered the highest grain yield in direct-seeded rice. Straw yield followed the same trend as grain yield. The harvest index was highest in anilophos and it was on a par with that of other herbicides and hand weeding (Table 2). In India, herbicide usage is increasing because of the high labor requirement for hand weeding (50 labor days ha⁻¹ × Rs 45) and scarcity of labor during peak periods of weeding. Also, herbicides are

available locally at a cheaper cost (Rs 250–300 L⁻¹, US\$1 = Rs 48) in emulsified concentration, which does not require a sprayer and can be applied easily as a sand mix by farmers. Hence, it could be concluded that all the herbicides, preferably anilophos (0.3 kg ai ha⁻¹), pretilachlor (0.4 kg ai ha⁻¹), and butanil (1.0 kg ai ha⁻¹), could be applied as preemergence herbicide at 8 DAS for better WCE and higher grain yield in wet-seeded rice.

References

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Table 1. Effect of weed control treatments on weed flora and weed control efficiency in wet-seeded rice.

Treatment	Weed number (no. m ⁻²)		Weed dry weight (g m ⁻²)		Weed control efficiency (%)		
	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet	Dry	Mean
T ₁ = unweeded check	1.5 ^a (29.5) ^b	2.5 (344.0)	1.49 (31.4)	2.31 (206.4)	–	–	–
T ₂ = hand weeding	1.3 (18.3)	2.4 (228.0)	1.36 (23.3)	2.04 (109.9)	38.0	33.7	35.9
T ₃ = butachlor (1.0 kg ai ha ⁻¹)	1.2 (16.8)	2.3 (190.0)	1.29 (19.6)	1.33 (22.0)	43.1	44.8	44.0
T ₄ = butanil (1.0 kg ai ha ⁻¹)	1.1 (12.1)	2.2 (144.7)	1.27 (18.7)	1.41 (25.5)	59.0	57.9	58.4
T ₅ = pretilachlor (0.4 kg ai ha ⁻¹)	1.1 (12.9)	2.2 (154.3)	1.15 (14.2)	1.32 (21.1)	56.3	55.1	55.7
T ₆ = pretilachlor + safener (0.4 kg ai ha ⁻¹)	1.3 (18.1)	2.2 (142.7)	1.27 (19.0)	1.47 (29.7)	38.6	58.6	48.6
T ₇ = anilophos (0.3 kg ai ha ⁻¹)	1.2 (14.3)	2.1 (125.3)	1.16 (14.5)	1.31 (20.3)	51.5	63.6	57.6
CD (P = 0.05)	0.09	0.07	0.13	0.11	na ^c	na	na

^aLogarithmic transformed values. ^bNumbers in parentheses indicate original values. ^cna = not analyzed.

Table 2. Effect of weed control treatments on yield and harvest index of wet-seeded rice.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Harvest index		
	Wet	Dry	Mean	Wet	Dry	Mean	Wet	Dry	Mean
T ₁ = unweeded check	3.9	3.2	3.5	8.5	8.0	8.1	0.32	0.29	0.30
T ₂ = hand weeding	5.3	4.2	4.8	8.6	8.6	8.6	0.38	0.33	0.36
T ₃ = butachlor (1.0 kg ai ha ⁻¹)	5.0	4.8	4.9	9.0	8.9	8.9	0.36	0.35	0.36
T ₄ = butanil (1.0 kg ai ha ⁻¹)	5.4	5.1	5.3	9.6	9.1	9.3	0.36	0.36	0.36
T ₅ = pretilachlor (0.4 kg ai ha ⁻¹)	5.4	5.2	5.3	9.6	9.1	9.4	0.36	0.36	0.36
T ₆ = pretilachlor + safener (0.4 kg ai ha ⁻¹)	5.2	4.8	5.0	9.4	8.9	9.1	0.36	0.35	0.35
T ₇ = anilophos (0.3 kg ai ha ⁻¹)	5.4	5.2	5.3	9.4	9.1	9.2	0.37	0.36	0.37
CD (P = 0.05)	0.19	0.24	0.19	ns	0.20	0.45	0.03	0.01	0.02

CD = critical difference.